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SÃO JOAQUIM STATE SCHOOL AND HEALTH SURVEILLANCE IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF CONCEIÇÃO DO MATO DENTRO RAISING AWARENESS ABOUT DENGUE

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ABSTRACT:

The objective of this work was to give a lecture with an educational approach, carried out through a partnership between Municipal Health Surveillance and the São Joaquim State School for the prevention of dengue in the Municipality of Conceição do Mato Dentro. The lecture took place at the school during the month of March 2022 for about 300 elementary school students, where 40 students were evaluated and the data reported within this research. In the lecture, tools for mosquito identification, disease symptoms, prevention and measures to combat the vector were shared. An increase in knowledge was observed after interventions resulting from the School and Surveillance partnership, positive actions that will be repeated not only in epidemic periods, but also at other times.